

1 **Supplementary Text**

2 **1. Issues with using Percentage Feeding Time in Phylogenetic Comparative Analyses.** First, though
3 percentage feeding time on food components (e.g. fruit) was used in many previous analyses, including those
4 employing phylogenetic comparative methods (e.g. Barton 1996; DeCasien et al. 2017), this type of data
5 violates the assumptions of phylogenetic comparative methods based on the Brownian-motion and Ornstein-
6 Uhlenbeck framework. These models assume that trait evolution is unbounded, and percentages do not behave
7 in this manner. Second, previous categorical classification schemes that attempted to fit percentage feeding time
8 data into categories that accurately reflect the diversity of primate diets (e.g., folivore, frugivore,
9 folivore/frugivore, frugivore/folivore, insectivore, omnivore, gummivore) result in increasingly complex models
10 with decreasing power. In addition, the small number of species in some of these categories (e.g., insectivores
11 and gummivores) means that parameter estimates based on these categories will be highly unreliable. Our
12 scheme is one of the simplest possible, describing broad groupings of primate diets, and thus should have
13 greatly increased statistical power.

14

15 **2. SIMMAP Modeling.** To incorporate uncertainty in the evolutionary history of our discrete predictors, diet
16 and social categories were first mapped on the full phylogeny using stochastic character mapping (SIMMAP).
17 We used the `make.simmap` function from the R package `phytools` (Revell 2011) to fit a continuous time-
18 reversible Markov-chain model and use that model to simulate stochastic character states on our phylogeny. For
19 each model including discrete predictors, we chose the rate model that best fit the data (via AICc) for the
20 transition rate matrix given the possibilities: Equal Rates (ER), Symmetric (SYM) or All Rates Different (ARD;
21 Table S1). After running all SIMMAPs in *slouch*, their AICc distributions were used to qualitatively inform our
22 model selection process and the SIMMAPs were summarized using the `describe.simmap` function (Revell
23 2011), with regimes assigned based on the maximum a posterior probability for each node using the transition
24 rate matrix with the lowest AICc score. These summarized SIMMAPs were used in our main *slouch* analysis.

25

26 *All Primates:* Our results incorporating uncertainty in regime placement for all primates show that models that
27 include diet (strict folivorous/non-folivorous), mating system, and activity period, tend to have AICc
28 distributions shifted towards relatively lower AICc values, though the combination of diet (strict folivorous/non-
29 folivorous) and mating system also stands out in also having lower AICc values (Fig. S1-S2).

30 *Strepsirrhines*: Our results for strepsirrhines show that models that include group size and sociality (social or
31 mating system) along with activity period tend to have AICc distributions shifted towards relatively lower AICc
32 values (Fig. S3-S4).

33 *Haplorhines*: Our results for haplorhines show that models that include folivorous diet (strict folivorous/non-
34 folivorous) and mating system have AICc distributions shifted towards relatively lower AICc values (Fig. S5-
35 S6).

36 *Platyrrhines*: Our results for platyrrhines show that models that including diet categories (strict folivorous/non)
37 and mating system or group size, and group size categories separately tend to have AICc distributions shifted
38 towards lower AICc values (Fig. S7-S8).

39

40 **3. bayou results.** Our best fitting *bayou* model (Fig. 1) showed an additional split along the lineage that led to
41 *Daubentonia madagascariensis*, which has the largest endocranial volume relative to body mass of any
42 strepsirrhine (Isler et al. 2008), with a posterior probability slightly less than our 0.5 cutoff ($pp = 0.389$). As
43 pointed out previously (Uyeda et al. 2017), it is currently impossible to determine if shifts on branches leading
44 to singleton taxa are the result of shifts in the slope and intercept or just the intercept. Therefore, to facilitate
45 analyses and interpretation of our results, we used the *bayou*-located two major shifts to inform our *slouch*
46 analyses: near the origin of haplorhines (after the split of tarsiers) and within platyrrhines.

47 Our two major shifts in primate brain size were among the more than 10 located in a recent study
48 (Miller et al. 2019) that focused on hominin brain evolution, and among the six shifts in intercept and slope in
49 another (Smaers et al. 2021) using the same overall approach. Our divergent results are most likely due to two
50 major differences – 1) we did not include fossil brain and body size estimates and thus our tree was ultrametric;
51 and 2) neither previous study accounted for measurement error in either brain or body size. As this study
52 specifically focuses on the effect of dietary and social factors (which can only be inferred from fossils with
53 caution) on non-human primate brain size, the first point could not be addressed here, but with regards to the
54 second, not accounting for measurement error can have major effects on parameters estimated from OU models
55 (Hansen and Bartoszek 2012; Uyeda et al. 2017).

56 We note that the lower slope (0.56) and relatively shorter half-life (67% of tree height) in the *bayou*
57 model with shifts is distinct from the model without any shifts (0.59 and infinity half-life, respectively; Table
58 S2), which is similar to our previous results (Grabowski et al. 2016) using an equivalent evolutionary model.

59 These results make sense as we are explaining and explaining more residual phylogenetic signal (lowering half-
60 life) by adding shifts as parameters in the model.

61 We incorporated the two shifts found by *bayou* on the phylogeny as fixed regimes to test if the
62 combination of the located shifts and a subset of our predictors explains brain size variation better than a model
63 without the shifts. Because these shifts are of the same type as our categorical data, the models in this subset
64 included the *bayou* shifts and the continuous predictor variable – group size. Here, the best model did not
65 include any of the continuous predictors and explained 15% more of the residual variance in brain size than the
66 model that included only body mass (Table S5), but the *bayou* model performed 6.9 AICc units worse than the
67 best model found above (e.g. diet plus average group size plus mating system) and explained about 18% less of
68 the residual R^2 . This result suggests that while shifts in our categorical predictors may correspond to at least
69 some of the *bayou*-located shifts, the combination of diet categories and sociality has greater explanatory power.

70

71 **4. All Primates**

72 **Contrasts between Evolutionary Trends Calculations.** While *slouch* calculates contrasts between trends
73 automatically, below we expand on how these contrasts are calculated from the trend parameter estimates in
74 Table 2 and Table S4 for the best fitting All Primates model, Diet Categories (Strict Folivorous/Non-folivorous)
75 + Group Size + Mating System.

76 Since all species are extant, the trends are only meaningful as contrasts with each other, and not as
77 estimates of absolute trends (Hansen 1997). Hence, we express them as contrasts between different adaptive
78 regimes. For example, a contrast of $5\% \text{ myr}^{-1}$ when switching from spatial polygyny to polygynandry would
79 mean that after 1 *myr*, relative endocranial volume is expected to be 5% larger in the polygynandric regime than
80 it would have been in the polygynic regime. This comparison does not say anything about the absolute rate of
81 increase, which could be positive or negative, only about the relative rate of change in brain size expected when
82 shifting from one regime to another. Contrasts between trends are calculated automatically in *slouch*, but we
83 give a specific example of how this calculation is performed using the estimated trends below. Simply put, as
84 trends are in units of trait units (log ECV in cm^3) per units of the phylogeny (here scaled to unit height = 1
85 except for the *bayou* analyses), the exponent of the difference between them (the “contrast”) is the expected
86 percentage change in relative brain size per unit of the phylogeny.

87

88 Below are examples of the trends discussed in the main text. We then show how the contrasts are transformed
89 into biologically relevant parameters.

90

91 **Shift from Non-folivorous Spatial Polygyny to Non-folivorous Polygynandry**

92 Parameter estimate of Non-folivorous Polygynandry = -0.17 ± 0.31

93 Parameter estimate of Non-folivorous Spatial Polygyny = -1.28 ± 0.21

94 *Slouch*-produced contrast between two regimes, in this case moving from the second to first = 1.11 ± 0.27

95

96 **Example contrast calculations between parameters:**

97 $\exp(-0.17 - -1.28) = \exp(1.11) = 3.034 = 303.4\%$ increase in brain size due to the regime shift over the time
98 span of the phylogeny (73 *myr*).

99

100 **Average Group Size Effect.** The parameter estimate of the effect of log average group size on log endocranial
101 volume is -0.08 ± 0.03 . This parameter estimate means that for every unit change in log average group size, log
102 endocranial volume decreases by half this amount, or 4% decrease over the time span of the phylogeny. This
103 result means that doubling average group size leads to about a 2.7% reduction in endocranial volume per tree
104 height (see calculation below).

105

106 **Effect of doubling average group size over the height of the phylogeny**

107 Parameter estimate of log Average Group Size = -0.08 ± 0.03

108 $1 - \exp((\log(2) * -0.04)) = 0.027 = 2.7\%$ decrease over the time span of the phylogeny (73 *myr*)

109

110 **5. Strepsirrhines**

111 **Average Group Size Effect.** The parameter estimate of the effect of log average group size on log endocranial
112 volume is -0.53 ± 0.11 . This parameter estimate is means that doubling average group size leads to a 16.8%
113 reduction in endocranial volume over the time span of the phylogeny. Data from Table S7.

114

115 **Effect of doubling average group size over the time span of the phylogeny**

116 Parameter estimate of log Average Group Size = -0.53 ± 0.11 .

117 $1 - \exp(\log(2) * -0.265) = 0.168 = 16.8\%$ decrease over the time span of the phylogeny (73 *myr*)

118 **Adaptive Optima for Diet (Folivorous/Non-folivorous) as the only predictor.** Based on the reconstructed
119 transitions in the phylogeny, shifting from a non-folivorous to folivorous diet leads to a 28.1% smaller optimal
120 brain size. Data from Tables S6, S7 and corresponding to Figs. S15, S16.

121

122 **Shift from Non-folivorous to Folivorous diet**

123 Parameter estimate of Folivorous: $= -2.70 \pm 0.28$

124 Parameter estimate of Non-folivorous: -2.37 ± 0.22

125 $1 - \exp(-2.70 - -2.37) = 0.281 = 28.1\%$ decrease

126

127 **Shift from Diurnal Monogamy to Diurnal Polygynandry**

128 Parameter estimate of Diurnal Monogamy: 0.14 ± 0.49

129 Parameter estimate of Diurnal Polygynandry: $= 1.42 \pm 0.77$

130 $\exp(1.42 - .14) = 3.597 = 359.7\%$ increase

131

132 **6. Platyrrhines**

133 **Adaptive Optima for Diet + Mating System Model**

134 Based on the reconstructed transitions in the phylogeny, shifting from non-folivorous polygynandry to non-
135 folivorous polyandry leads to a 52% decrease in brain size with a half-life of only 6% of tree length or 1.32 *myr*.

136 Data from Table S11 and corresponding to Fig. 2d and Fig. S13.

137

138 **Shift from Non-folivorous polygynandry to Non-folivorous polyandry**

139 Parameter Estimate of Non-folivorous Polygynandry: -0.85 ± 0.29

140 Parameter Estimate of Non-folivorous Polyandry: -1.58 ± 0.21

141 $1 - \exp(-1.58 - -0.85) = 0.518 = 51.8\%$ decrease

142

143 **Shift from Non-folivorous polygynandry to Non-folivorous harem polygyny**

144 Parameter Estimate of Non-folivorous Polygynandry: -0.85 ± 0.29

145 Parameter Estimate of Non-folivorous Harem Polygyny: -0.05 ± 0.36

146 $\exp(-0.05 - -0.85) = 2.225 = 222.5\%$ increase

147

148 **7. Sex specific analyses.** We repeated all analyses using samples consisting of solely of species averages for
149 males and females, which overall mirrored our species-wide results (Table 12). For the complete dataset, the
150 best model for males was diet (strict folivorous /non-folivorous) plus group size plus mating system, while for
151 females it was diet plus group size categories plus mating system. For strepsirrhines, results for both sexes were
152 the same, but the best model included diet categories (strict folivorous /non-folivorous) rather than mating
153 system, along with group size and activity period. For haplorhines, while females were the same as for the all-
154 primate group, the best model for males was diet (strict folivorous /non- folivorous) plus group size plus mating
155 system. For platyrrhines, the best model for females was diet (strict folivorous /non- folivorous) plus group size
156 plus mating system while for males it was diet (strict folivorous /non- folivorous) plus group size categories.
157 Note also that the estimated half-life for male and female platyrrhines was distinct, with 86% of the phylogeny
158 length for females and 245% of the phylogeny length for males. Difference between the sexes in the rate of
159 adaptation was also found previously in primate body size (Grabowski and Jungers 2017).

160

161 **8. Single predictors and effects of measurement error.** We re-ran our analyses using single predictors for our
162 complete dataset, which optimizes the sample size for each analysis. As sample size and composition varies for
163 each predictor, these models are therefore not directly comparable to each other, only to the allometric model
164 for each sample, but larger sample sizes can potentially reveal patterns that are useful in interpreting our main
165 results. Overall results (Table S13) are consistent with the findings for the dataset used in our main analysis –
166 diet (frugivorous/non-frugivorous and folivorous /non- folivorous) and sociality (social system, mating system,
167 and group size categories) were substantially better than the allometric model in each analysis, but their
168 relatively small residual R^2 values when compared to our results above speaks to the importance of using
169 multiple predictors. To test if including measurement error in the species means was driving the differences in
170 our results when compared to previous findings, we re-ran our all-primate species-level analyses but did not
171 account for measurement error. Results (Table S14) were consistent with our previous findings, though there
172 was an overall decrease in the half-lives and reduction in likelihood as expected when not accounting for
173 measurement error in the model (Hansen and Bartoszek 2012). It is obvious from our selection of studies
174 included here (Table 1) that not all predictors were tested. Home range size, day range, and other predictors
175 were all factors previously noted as affecting brain size, and these are not included. As we seek to run models
176 with all predictors, the chief issue with including every possible predictor is that it reduces sample size and
177 increases the number of parameters to estimate, leading to increasingly poor estimates.

178 **9. Haplorhines**

179 **Contrasts between Evolutionary Trends for model with Mating System as the only predictor**

180 Based on the reconstructed transitions in the phylogeny, shifting from to harem polygyny from polygynandry
181 leads to a 48.3% decrease in brain size over the length of the phylogeny. Data from Table S9 and corresponding
182 to Fig. S17.

183

184 **Shift to Harem Polygyny from Polygynandry**

185 Parameter estimate of Harem Polygyny = -0.75 ± 0.58

186 Parameter estimate of Polygynandry = -0.09 ± 0.49

187 *Slouch*-produced contrast between two regimes, in this case moving from the second to first = -0.65 ± 0.33

188

189 **Example contrast calculations between parameters:**

190 $1 - \exp(-0.75 - (-0.09)) = 0.483 = 48.3\%$ decrease in brain size due to the regime shift over the time span of the
191 phylogeny (73 myr).

192

193

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- 219

Fig. S1

Supplementary Figure S1: First half of AICc distributions from SIMMAPs for models for all primates.

Fig. S2

Supplementary Figure S2: Second half of AICc distributions from SIMMAPs for models for all primates.

Fig. S3

Supplementary Figure S3: First half of AICc distributions from SIMMAPs for models for strepsirrhines plus tarsiers.

Fig. S4

Supplementary Figure S4: Second half of AICc distributions from SIMMAPs for models for strepsirrhines plus tarsiers.

Fig. S5

Supplementary Figure S5: First half of AICc distributions from SIMMAPs for models for haplorhines minus tarsiers.

Fig. S6

Supplementary Figure S6: Second half of AICc distributions from SIMMAPs for models for haplorhines minus tarsiers.

Fig. S7

Supplementary Figure S7: First half of AICc distributions from SIMMAPs for models for platyrrhines.

Fig. S8

Supplementary Figure S8: Second half of AICc distributions from SIMMAPs for models including platyrrhines.

Fig. S9

Supplementary Figure S9: Same as Fig. 1 but with species names.

Fig. S10

Supplementary Figure S10: a) log Endocranial Volume against log Body Mass for all primate species in this analyses with lines showing expected magnitude of difference among evolutionary trends in the diet categories and mating system regimes after 73 *myr* of evolution, which is the height of the complete phylogeny, with folivorous diet denoted by dashed lines; b) phylogeny with branches coded by ancestral state reconstruction of regimes matching a). Figure corresponds to Fig. 2a.

Fig. S11

Supplementary Figure S11: a) log Endocranial Volume against log Body Mass for strepsirrhine species plus tarsiers in this analyses with lines showing expected magnitude of difference among evolutionary trends mating system and activity period regimes after 73 *myr* of evolution, which is the height of the complete phylogeny; b) phylogeny with branches coded by ancestral state reconstruction of matching regimes. Species with the largest relative brain size here is *Daubentonia madagascariensis* as found in Isler et al. (2008). Figure corresponds to Fig. 2b.

Fig. S12

Supplementary Figure S12: a) log Endocranial Volume against log Body Mass for haplorhine species minus tarsiers in this analyses with lines showing expected magnitude of difference among evolutionary trends in the diet categories + mating system regimes after 73 *myr* of evolution, which is the height of the complete phylogeny, with folivorous denoted by dashed lines; b) phylogeny with branches coded by ancestral state reconstruction of matching regimes. Figure corresponds to Fig. 2c.

Fig. S13

Supplementary Figure S13: a) log Endocranial Volume against log Body Mass for platyrrhine species in this analyses with regression lines showing the adaptive optima for each category; b) phylogeny with branches coded by ancestral state reconstruction of matching regimes. Figure corresponds to Fig. 2d.

Fig. S14

Supplementary Figure S15: Same as Supplementary Figure S10 but with shapes denoting families and a selection of labeled points.

Fig. S15

Supplementary Figure S15: Estimated adaptive optima for each diet category with standard error bars and individual species values shown in smaller symbols. Approach following Fig. 2.

Fig. S16

a)

b)

Supplementary Figure S16: a) log Endocranial Volume against log Body Mass for strepsirrhine species plus tarsiers in this analyses with regression lines showing the adaptive optima for each diet category (folivorous/non-folivorous); b) phylogeny with branches color coded ancestral state reconstruction. Color coding in both figures matches the legend. Figure corresponds to Supplementary Fig. S15.

Fig. S17

Supplementary Figure S17: a) log Endocranial Volume against log Body Mass for haplorhine species in this analyses with lines showing expected magnitude of difference among evolutionary trends in the mating system regimes after 73 *myr* of evolution, which is the height of the complete phylogeny; b) phylogeny with branches color coded by ancestral state reconstruction. Color coding in both figures matches the legend. Note spatial polygyny and monogamy have nearly the same parameter value and are masking each other.